

**A STUDY ON JOB INVOLVEMENT AND LIFE
SATISFACTION AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Abstract:

Education is considered as the most powerful weapon of life to get victory and success. The teachers plays great role towards education and shape up both present and future of a student. Teachers serve a great job in making the good society by educating and guiding number of student in their whole life. Satisfaction is the favorableness or unfavourableness with which employees view their work. Job involvement and Life satisfaction of primary school teachers are found to be influenced by several factors like gender, religion, type of the school, nature of the school, education qualification, nature of appointment, location of the school, marital status, monthly income, years of experience etc. It seems that many prefer the teaching profession out of parents or somebody's compulsion and not out of their own genuine interest. For this a sample of 294 was collected from primary school teachers of various schools and t-test and Anova were used as statistical tools to analyse the data. The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between gender, educational qualification and job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers. While taking decision on and job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers their gender and educational qualification has to be taken for decision making process.

Key Words: Education, Job Involvement & Satisfaction

Introduction:

The teacher's profession is considered as the best and ideal profession in this world as they provide selfless duty to shape someone's life. Their committed work cannot be compared to anything. Teachers are those who always take care of their all students. They check their food habits, cleanliness level, behaviour to others and concentration towards study. They check our nails weekly to maintain cleanliness and hygiene and prevent us from diseases. Education is considered as the most powerful weapon of life to get victory and success. This great responsibility and job is given to the teachers to nourish and shape up the lives of young lives of young ones and future of their country. The teachers plays great role towards education and shape up both present and future of a student. Teachers serve a great job in making the good society by educating and guiding number of student in their whole life. Teachers are especially send by the god to lead people on right path in the life as well as make them able to take right decisions in bad situation they lead young ones from their childhood and make them fit mentally, socially and intellectually teachers are like common people who are from between us but they choose to do unusual job of teaching to their students.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of job involvement of primary school teachers.
- ✓ To find out the level of life satisfaction of primary school teachers.
- ✓ To find out the relationship between job involvement and life satisfaction of primary school teachers.

Need and Scope of the Study:

The country is nowadays in the hands of the teachers. It is in the sense that teacher produces citizens of a country who will be rulers of the future. Whatever may be positions held, all the citizens are serving the nation. The teacher plays a key role in the educational system for its success or failure. Teaching profession is different from other professions. Few teachers realize this fact. Every teacher should know the peculiarities of his profession and the new role assigned to him in the educational system. The importance of the teacher in any educational system lies in the attitude possessed by them towards their profession. Job involvement and Life satisfaction of primary school teachers are found to be influenced by several factors like gender, religion, type of the school, nature of the school, education qualification, nature of appointment, location of the school, marital status, monthly income, years of experience etc. It seems that many prefer the teaching profession out of parents or somebody's compulsion and not out of their own genuine interest.

Review of Related Literature:

Malhotra (2002) examines the benefits of inclusive education. It points out the need for realized the similarities and respecting the difference among children in inclusive schools. The paper also discusses the change in practice in education of children with special needs and the enormity of the task achieving inclusion in schools.

Julka (2002) presented an article which brings out a respective of the developing countries like India, Bhutan, Nepal and Maldives for inclusive education. The education system in these countries has gone through

a number of upheavals. Four country reports presented at the international need assessment workshop held in New Delhi were qualitatively analyzed to understand the existing situation in these countries. The countries having geographical proximity but not homogeneous. Comparisons were made in terms of policy issues, conceptual issues, and teacher training, research and support structure.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The investigator delimited to the schools available in Coimbatore district.
- ✓ The sample of 294 teachers is enrolled.
- ✓ There may be a bias in collection of primary data

Methodology:

Design of the Study: The researcher has identified a problem to investigate the job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers.

Sample of the Study: The sample for the investigation consisted of 294 primary school teachers of Kids kingdom nursery, M.J. Vincent Metric School, Vincent higher secondary school.

Tools Used for the Study: T-test and Anova

Analysis and Interpretation:

H01: There will be significant mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on gender (male / female)

Table 1: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on gender

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	p value	Result
Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on gender	Male	46	1.3404	.11946	298	0.838	0.007	S
	Female	254	1.3233	.12927				
	Total	300	1.3259	.12777				

Interpretation:

The table 1 shows the mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on gender (male / female). The calculated t-value is statistically not significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 1 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on gender.

H02: There will be significant mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on educational qualification (UG / PG)

Table 2: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on educational qualification

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on educational qualification	UG	220	1.3264	.12289	298	0.104	0.011	S
	PG	80	1.3246	.13931				
	Total	300	1.3290	.12777				

Interpretation:

The table 2 shows the mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on educational qualification (UG / PG). The calculated t-value is statistically not significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 1 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on educational qualification.

H03: There will be significant mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on group (science / arts)

Table 3: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on group

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on group	Science	131	1.3102	.14474	298	-1.887	0.060	NS
	Arts	169	1.3381	.11180				
	Total	300	1.3290	.12686				

Interpretation:

The table 3 shows the mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on group (science/arts). The calculated t-value is statistically not significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 3 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on group studying of the respondents.

H04: There will be significant mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on location of the school (rural / urban)

Table 4: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on location of the school

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on location of the school	Rural	7	1.1000	.00000	298	-4.913	0.000	S
	Urban	293	1.3313	.12435				
	Total	300	1.3290	.12686				

Interpretation:

The table 4 shows the mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on location of the school (rural / urban). The calculated t-value is statistically not significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 4 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers based on location of the school.

Findings:

- ✓ There is no significant relationship between Institution studying with and factors related to Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between gender and Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between educational qualification and factors related to educational qualification and life satisfaction among primary school teachers.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between group and factors related to group and life satisfaction among primary school teachers.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between location of the school and factors related to Job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers.

Suggestions:

- ✓ It is recommended that changes can be made in the work timings and the timing can be changed to 8.30 to 5.30, so that teacher involvement level will be increased.
- ✓ One should provide the facilities to employees like child-care, play- house and school nearby employees' quarters so that separate family employees can live tension free.
- ✓ The communication between the supervisors and the subordinates can be improved regarding the work , the information's regarding the work can be communicated or explained directly by the supervisors to the sub-ordinates so that the communication gap between them can be reduced.
- ✓ Suggestion box can be placed for getting suggestions from the teachers for the empowerment of the organisation in future period of time.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between gender, educational qualification and job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers. While taking decision on and job involvement and life satisfaction among primary school teachers their gender and educational qualification has to be taken for decision making process.

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